

Original Research

Financial Management in Tourism Awareness Groups of Central Lombok Regency: Motivation, Competence, and Accountability Behavior

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Abstract

This study aims to evaluate the effects of motivation, competence, and accountability on financial management. The research adopts an associative approach with a quantitative methodology, utilizing primary data. The study population includes all Tourism Awareness Groups (Pokdarwis) in the tourist villages of Central Lombok Regency. The sample consists of 13 Pokdarwis from 13 different tourist villages, totaling 65 respondents, selected through purposive sampling. The findings reveal that: (1) motivation does not have a significant effect on financial management; (2) competence also does not significantly influence financial management; and (3) accountability behavior has a positive and significant impact on financial management. This research aims to inform and support government decision-making, particularly for regional government agencies (OPD) in Central Lombok Regency, in enhancing financial management practices to support the development of tourist villages. Additionally, the findings may serve as a reference and evaluative tool for future government budgeting strategies, especially in areas designated for tourism management and development.

Keywords: Accountability Behavior, Competence, Financial Management, Motivation.

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Introduction

A village constitutes the smallest governmental unit, governed by its own regulations, possessing the authority to administer its territory, communal assets, and finances to enhance the welfare and quality of life of its inhabitants, thereby mitigating regional disparities, poverty, and various socio-cultural challenges. A tourist hamlet, referred to as Kampung, Nagari, Gampong, or other designations, is characterized as a locale possessing unique and distinctive tourist attractions. The categorization of tourist villages, as outlined in the Tourist Village Guidelines published by the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Investment Coordination, includes pioneering, developing, advanced, and independent tourist villages. Simultaneously, the operational management of a tourist village, as outlined in the Tourist Village Guidelines, is executed by three entities: Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDesa), Village Cooperatives, and the Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis). The financial sources for the tourist village, as outlined in the Tourist Village Guidelines, include three primary sources: government allocations in the form of Village Funds, the State Budget (APBN), the Provincial Regional Budget (APBD), and the District/City Regional Budget (APBD). The second financing source is derived from Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), while the third source originates from other non-binding avenues. The book "Guidelines for the Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis)" states that funding sources are derived from the self-sufficiency of Pokdarwis members, specifically by revitalizing entertainment activities through partnerships with tourism enterprises, sponsors, and the community, which are legitimate, non-binding, and compliant with applicable regulations. Funding sources are derived from profit-sharing related to attraction management, as well as the sale of catering services, crafts, souvenirs, and other goods and services made by Pokdarwis in the tourist hamlet (Rahim, 2012).

Financial management in Pokdarwis for managing a tourist village is carried out by applying the Macro Small Medium Entity Accounting Standards (SAK-EMKM). This aims to enable small businesses to prepare their own financial statements and be audited without external assistance (Maretha, et al., 2020). The accounting transaction recording system aims to obtain information related to the flow of financial transactions and the financial position of a business. The flow of financial transactions describes the inflow from sales cash and the outflow for expenses (Saputra et al., 2018). Most small business operators do not maintain proper financial records, making it difficult for them to assess their business results and development, and they are unable to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of their business management. The principles in business management that are applied rely solely on experience and habits to support the continuity of the business (Poernamawatie et al., 2023).

The Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis) has several business activities to manage in order to generate income, so a structured and clear financial management system is very much needed. The guidelines for the Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis) issued by the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy state that the size of an organization's structure is determined by the number of its members. Therefore, Pokdarwis with a relatively large membership will be required to establish several sections or units to handle different areas of activity and create group references and regulations in the form

of Articles of Association/Household Budget (AD/ART). Other regulations related to financial management procedures for Pokdarwis are not detailed in the guidelines, which has initiated several service, mentoring, and training activities for Pokdarwis in tourist villages, focusing on financial management for the Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis) as conducted by (Andriana et al., 2022; Geria, 2021; Siregar et al., 2022)..

Factors that influence financial management include motivation, where the focus of the research is on individuals who carry out the financial management of the organization, as explained in the studies (Hamzah & Mardiaty, 2017; Jaya, 2011; Asah et al., 2015; Rosalina et al., 2021; Rosnidah et al., 2022; Safwan et al., 2014; Wang & Redmond, 2006; Widiatmika & Darma, 2018). Furthermore, the factor of human resource competence also influences financial management and is explained in the research (Estrilia et al., 2023; Pituringsih et al., 2020; Puspa & Prasetyo, 2020; Rosnidah et al., 2022; Safwan et al., 2014; Wardiana & Hermanto, 2019). Other studies also add the level or degree of education of business actors that influences financial management, as stated in Karadag, (2017); Mustika, (2021). It is also mentioned that accountability has an influence on the financial management of an organization (Estrilia et al., 2023; Yuanita & Suropto, 2022; Wisastrawan et al., 2020; Asmawati & Basuki, 2019; Astawa & Dewi, 2021; Bakhtiar, 2021; Saputra, et al., 2018; Sari et al., 2018; Umami & Nurodin, 2017). The relationship between accountability and financial management explains the connection between accountability behavior, which is defined as the behavior of being accountable, becoming one of the factors that influence financial management, and this is explained in the research (Limba et al., 2020; Pratiwi et al., 2018). In managing finances, the managers of Pokdarwis come from the village community, which has diverse educational backgrounds, abilities, motivations, intentions, and mindsets that shape their financial management behavior. Therefore, the factors of motivation, competence, and accountability behavior are considered the most suitable variables for analyzing financial management in the Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis) that manages a tourist village.

The designation of West Nusa Tenggara Province as one of the super priority destinations has an impact on development in the regions, especially Lombok Island which has been designated as the Mandalika Special Economic Zone (KEK). This was also conveyed by Amir et al., (2020), where the establishment of the Mandalika Special Economic Zone (SEZ) is expected to act as a catalyst for the tourism sector in Lombok, which has been continuously developing over the past ten years. The evidence is the announcement of 99 tourist villages developed and approved by the West Nusa Tenggara Provincial Tourism Office. The province of West Nusa Tenggara, specifically Central Lombok Regency, has announced the number of tourist villages registered with the Central Lombok Regency Tourism Office in 2020 and has been ratified in a decree. Here is the number of tourist villages in Central Lombok Regency based on their classification:

Table 1. Number of Tourist Villages in Central Lombok in 2020 Based on the Decree of the Regent of Central Lombok

Number	Category	Number of Tourist Villages
1	Startup	40
2	Develop	11
3	Advance	1
4	Independent	0

Source: Central Lombok Regency Tourism Office

Based on Table 1, it can be seen that the number of tourism villages categorized as pioneering in the Central Lombok Regency area is more than the other three categories. In the table, there is also a noticeable gap between the number of advanced tourist villages and those categorized as pioneering and developing. This may indicate that improvements are still needed in terms of management and operations to develop these tourist villages. In addition, the number of pilot tourist villages in the table above can also provide an overview of the enthusiasm of the village community to develop their village's potential through tourism business activities. The growth of tourist villages in Central Lombok Regency is one of the positive impacts of tourism development and is expected to become an alternative accommodation in the tourism sector in the region. The contribution from various parties to transform the category of pilot tourist villages into independent tourist villages is highly necessary. Therefore, the researchers are interested in conducting a study related to motivation, competence, accountability behavior, and financial management in the Tourism Awareness Group in the Tourism Village of Central Lombok Regency.

Literature Review

Stakeholder Theory

The stakeholder theory argues that an institution's success is significantly contingent upon its capacity to equilibrate the diverse interests of its associated stakeholders (Melinda et al., 2022). Moreover, the stakeholder theory articulated by Maulida et al., (2022) posits that an organization will endeavor to fulfill stakeholder expectations to maintain sustainability through the disclosure of pertinent information. The acquired information is derived from financial records, which provide financial statements that provide data for decision-making to address the challenges encountered by an institution. This study examines the financial management executed by the Tourism Awareness Group in a tourist hamlet as an application of stakeholder theory, reflecting the accountability of managers to stakeholders, including the government, investors, and the general public.

Theory of Planned Behavior

The theory is based on the fundamental premise that human behavior is carried out consciously and considers various information and experiences necessary for making a decision. The theory of planned behavior is a theory about the relationship between

beliefs and actions. The action referred to in this study is the action of being accountable in financial management. The capacity of Pokdarwis members in managing financial transactions, preparing financial reports, and conducting control is important because the funds obtained from other parties, whether from the government, private sector, or donations from community members, must be accountable based on the principles of transparency and accountability so that the performance of Pokdarwis can be trusted by the government or donors in managing finances (Muhartono dkk., 2022).

Framework and Hypothesis

Framework of Thought

Systematic, accountable, and transparent financial management has an impact on the independence of a tourist village. Good financial management in Pokdarwis is believed to enhance the organization's performance and increase its business revenue. By understanding the motivations and competencies of those managing Pokdarwis, it will provide insight into making important decisions for the organization. In addition, understanding the accountability behavior of Pokdarwis managers in financial management will instill trust in the community and funders.

Figure 1. Research Framework

Ningsih et al. (2023); Limba et al., (2020); Pratiwi, et al. (2022)

Hypothesis Development

Motivation on Financial Management

Motivation is a strong determinant of individual behavior. In addition, motivation is measured with psychological indicators. When individuals have high motivation, the results they produce tend to be high as well, and vice versa. The research conducted on motivation in financial management focuses on intrinsic motivation, as it aims to see how individuals have the desire to manage finances (Rosalina et al., 2021). Based on the

research results from Rosnidah et al., (2022), it is illustrated that the motivation variable has an influence on the regional financial management performance variable. It is stated that each employee actually has their own motivation that can serve as a spirit to drive and foster enthusiasm in working to achieve the organization's goals.

Stakeholder theory focuses more on the company's management as stakeholders. In addition, Stakeholder theory places greater emphasis on the higher needs in Maslow's hierarchy, particularly the need for achievement and the need for affiliation. In relation to employee motivation, there are three psychological states, namely the experience of understanding the work, the experience of responsibility for outcomes, and the understanding of the actual relationship. It is then stated that with good financial management, trust and motivation will be created for stakeholders to jointly advance the company (Ningsih et al., 2023). Based on the explanation, it can be elaborated that the higher the motivation of the managers, the more it influences the financial management carried out by the Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis).

H₁: Motivation positively impacts the financial management.

Competence on Financial Management

Competence is identical to the abilities and skills of employees in carrying out their work. This explains that to carry out good financial management, the competence skills of the managers in conducting financial management activities are required. This statement is also supported by research findings from Ilhami & Widhiastuti, (2022), which explain that good human resource competence will enhance financial management accountability. In addition, competence also falls into the very high category in improving financial management accountability, where the indicators of human resource competence in the study include knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Other research also emphasizes that human resource competence has an influence on financial management, but it is not very important if not supported by a clear system (Saputra et al., 2018).

The stakeholder theory is a theory that must provide benefits to all parties, where the company is not an entity that operates solely for the personal interests of the entity's owners, but rather pays attention to the parties involved. The connection between human resource competencies and stakeholder theory is linked in an effort to improve the financial performance of a company or organization. In the research by Ningsih et al. (2023), it is stated that the quality of financial management applied by MSMEs is still considered low. This is because many MSME actors do not engage in planning, recording, reporting, and controlling their businesses, which impacts their performance, development, and business sustainability. In the research, it is also explained that the low quality of financial management in MSMEs is partly influenced by limited knowledge, where knowledge is an indicator of human resource competence. Therefore, it can be said that business owners who possess competence will be able to be accountable to the parties involved in their business activities. Based on the above explanation, it can be said that the better the human resource competencies possessed, the more it will affect the financial management of the Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis).

H₂: Competence positively impacts the financial management.

Accountability Behavior on Financial Management

A person's behavior will be realized if there is an intention to behave. Generally, the stronger the intention to do something, the more likely it is to achieve a behavior. The assumption formed in the Planned Behavior Theory is that humans, as rational beings, use information that is available to them systematically. The three determinants, namely attitude towards accountability, subjective norms, and self-efficacy, provide relevant information in determining the intention to act accountably or adhere to accountability principles, especially in financial management (Limba et al., 2020).

Accountability behavior is the intention of a person or individual to perform a task that, in this study, is associated with responsible and accountable financial management. In the study conducted by Limba et al., (2020), it is explained that attitudes towards accountability, subjective norms, and self-efficacy as determinants that shape behavioral intentions (intentions to act accountably) both partially and simultaneously influence the behavior of village government officials in managing village finances. Additionally, research conducted by Pratiwi et al., (2018) also explains that these three factors can influence an individual's intention to exhibit or not exhibit transparency and accountability behavior in financial management. Based on the explanation, it can be interpreted that the accountability behavior possessed influences the good financial management of the Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis).

H₃: Accountability Behavior positively impacts the financial management.

Methodology

Research type and approach

This research uses a quantitative approach with data collection and analysis methods based on numbers or statistics to investigate and understand social phenomena related to the relationship between motivation, competence, accountability behavior, and financial management in the Tourism Awareness Group in the Tourism Village of Central Lombok Regency. There are 52 Tourism Awareness Groups (Pokdarwis), including 10 Tourism Awareness Groups that do not yet have an organization establishment permit/Decree. The reason for selecting the research location is that Central Lombok Regency is currently focused on tourism development. This is also due to the establishment of the Mandalika Special Economic Zone in the area, so the development of tourist villages as an alternative accommodation is expected to contribute positively to both the economy and sustainable tourism development.

Operational Variables

The operational variables of the research model are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Variable Definitions and Operations

Variables	Definition	Indicator
Motivation (X1)	Motivation is a mental condition that drives someone to engage in activities and provides the energy that leads to the fulfillment of needs, offers satisfaction, or reduces imbalance. (Pratiwi, et al., 2022)	1. Physiological Needs 2. The Need for a Sense of Security 3. Social Needs 4. Self-Esteem Needs 5. Self-Actualization Needs
Competence (X2)	Competence can be defined as the ability to perform a job or task based on skills and knowledge, supported by a work attitude, which in this research is related to financial management tasks (Ramdayanti, 2019).	1. Knowledge 2. Expertise 3. Attitude
Accountability Behavior (X3)	Accountability behavior is the result of a decision based on the tendency or intention to perform an action that supports or, conversely, does not support it. In this case, the tendency is to act in an accountable manner. (Amanah, 2023; Limba et al., 2020)	1. Attitude Toward Behavior 2. Subjective norm 3. Perceived Behavioral Control
Financial Management (Y)	Financial management according to Permendagri No. 20 of 2018 encompasses all activities including planning, implementation, administration, reporting, and accountability of village finances (Khadijah & Purba, 2021)	1. Financial planning 2. Financial recordkeeping 3. Financial reporting 4. Financial control

Source: Pratiwi, et al. (2022); Ramdayanti (2019); Amanah (2023); Limba et al. (2020); Khadijah & Purba (2021)

The population in this study consists of all the Tourism Awareness Groups (Pokdarwis) located in Central Lombok Regency. Therefore, the population of this study consists of 52 Tourism Awareness Groups (Pokdarwis) recorded by the Tourism Office. The sampling technique used in this study employs non-probability sampling with a purposive sampling approach. The sampling criteria are explained in Table 3.

Table 3. Research Sample

No.	Criteria	Total
1	Tourism Awareness Groups (Pokdarwis) recorded by the Tourism Office	52
2	Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis) that does not yet have a Decree of Establishment Confirmation	(1)
3	Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis) categorized as a Pilot	(38)
4	Total research sample	13

The number of respondents in this study is 65 people, who are the main managers of the Tourism Awareness Groups in the Tourism Villages of Central Lombok Regency. The number consists of the number of Pokdarwis managers from developing and advanced category tourist villages in Central Lombok Regency.

Data Analysis Technique

The data analysis method used in this study is the PLS-SEM method with the assistance of the Smart PLS version 4.0 program. PLS-SEM aims to test the predictive relationships between constructs by examining the relationships or influences among those constructs. PLS-SEM analysis consists of two submodels, namely the measurement model (outer model) and the structural model (inner model).

This research includes 3 (three) exogenous constructs and 1 (one) endogenous construct. Exogenous variables are variables that influence endogenous variables, including motivation, competence, and accountability behavior. Endogenous variables are dependent variables influenced by exogenous variables, namely financial management. There are at least five stages in Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) analysis, namely model conceptualization, determining the analysis algorithm method, determining the resampling method, drawing path diagrams, and model evaluation.

Results and Discussion

The response rate for the research questionnaire was 74.3% from the 70 questionnaires that were distributed. A total of 15 respondent answers were not returned because 3 tourist villages do not yet have a Decree of Confirmation for Pokdarwis and do not have active Pokdarwis. Meanwhile, 3 responses were not returned because the position of vice-chairman in 3 Sadar Wisata groups was unoccupied. Thus, the number of research respondents who answered is 52 respondents.

Outer Model

Figure 2 is the PLS path diagram of the research algorithm showing the loading factors of each reflective construct.

Figure 2. Outer Model

The motivation variable measured by the MO3 dimension can be reflected in the MO3.2 question instrument, and the MO4 dimension can be reflected in the MO4.1 and MO4.2 question instruments. The competence variable measured by KO1 can be reflected in the KO1.1 and KO1.2 question instruments; KO2 can be reflected in the KO2.1, KO2.2, and KO2.3 question instruments; and KO3 can be reflected in the KO3.2 question instrument. The image above also shows that the accountability behavior variable measured by the PA1 dimension can be reflected in the PA1.5, PA1.6, and PA1.7 question instruments; the PA2 dimension can be reflected in the PA2.1 and PA2.2 question instruments; and the PA3 dimension can be reflected in the PA3.1, PA3.2, and PA3.3 question instruments. The financial management variable measured by PK1 can be reflected with the question instruments PK1.1; PK1.5; PK1.6 and PK1.7; the PK2 dimension can be reflected with the question instruments PK2.1 and PK2.2; the PK3 dimension can be reflected with the question instruments PK3.1; PK3.4; PK3.5; PK3.6; PK3.7 and the PK4 dimension can be reflected with the question instrument PK4.5.

Table 4. Construct Reliability

Variable	Dimension	Outer Loading	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Motivation	MO4	1.000			
Competence	KO1	0.914	0.885	0.942	0.890
	KO2	0.972			
Accountability Behavior	PA1	0.845	0.837	0.897	0.743
	PA2	0.887			
	PA3	0.853			
Financial Management	PK1	0.877	0.884	0.917	0.736
	PK2	0.903			
	PK3	0.760			
	PK4	0.884			

Based on the Table 4, the motivation variable proxied by the self-esteem needs dimension (MO4) with an outer loading value of 1.00 indicates that the statement item is strongly correlated in explaining motivation. The reliability of the motivation variable is acceptable, but the AVE value and the composite reliability rho_c value for the motivation construct do not appear in the PLS-Algorithm output because they have an outer loading value of 1. Motivation is most strongly reflected by the dimension MO4, which is always involved in every decision-making process.

The competence variable, proxied by the knowledge dimension (KO1) and the skill dimension (KO2) with outer loading values of 0.914 and 0.972, respectively, shows that the 5 statement items from these 2 dimensions are strongly correlated in explaining competence. The reliability of the competence variable is acceptable with a composite reliability rho_c value of 0.942 > 0.70, Cronbach's alpha of 0.885 > 0.70, and an AVE value of 0.89 > 0.50. Competence is most strongly reflected by the KO2 dimension with

a loading factor of 0.972, which includes the ability to complete tasks as described in job descriptions, the ability to minimize errors in work, and the ability to solve problems that arise in the work being performed.

The accountability behavior variable, proxied by the dimensions of attitude toward behavior (PA1), subjective norm (PA2), and perceived behavioral control (PA3) with outer loading values of 0.845, 0.887, and 0.853, respectively, indicates that the 8 statement items from these three dimensions are strongly correlated in explaining accountability behavior. The reliability of the accountability behavior variable is acceptable with a composite reliability ρ_c value of $0.897 > 0.70$, Cronbach's alpha of $0.837 > 0.70$, and an AVE value of $0.743 > 0.50$. Accountability behavior is most strongly reflected by dimension PA2 with a loading factor of 0.887, which indicates that to make the organization's performance look good, the organization encourages the principle of accountability, and the leader or group head supports the principle of accountability so that the organization's budget performance looks good.

The financial management variable, represented by the financial planning dimension (PK1), financial recording dimension (PK2), financial reporting dimension (PK3), and control dimension (PK4) with a loading factor range of 0.760 – 0.903, indicates that the 12 questionnaire items from these four dimensions are strongly correlated in explaining financial management. The reliability of the financial management variable is acceptable with a composite reliability value ρ_c $0.17 > 0.70$, Cronbach's alpha $0.884 > 0.70$, and AVE value $0.736 > 0.50$. Financial management is most strongly reflected by the PK2 dimension with a loading factor of 0.903, which involves routinely recording sales and purchase transactions as well as regularly summarizing cash receipts and expenditures each month.

Inner Model

The evaluation of the structural model in this study was conducted by analyzing the Variance Inflated Factor (VIF), coefficient of determination (R^2), effect size (f^2), and predictive relevance (Q^2) to test predictive relevance, t-statistic value, and p-value for hypothesis testing and PLS Predict. The table shows the inner Variance Inflated Factor (VIF) size to observe multicollinearity among the following variables.

Table 5. Collinearity Statistic (VIF)

Paths	VIF
Motivation (X1) -> Financial Management (Y)	2.532
Competence (X2) -> Financial Management (Y)	1.175
Accountability Behavior (X3) -> Financial Management (Y)	2.605

The Variance Inflated Factor (VIF) value indicates the level of multicollinearity issues in the structural model. Based on Table 5, the inner VIF value is below 5, indicating a low level of multicollinearity among the variables. This result indicates that the parameter estimation results in SEM PLS are unbiased or robust.

Table 6. Determinant Coefficient or R-Square (R²)

Variable	R-square	R-square adjusted
Financial Management (Y)	0.357	0.317

Based on the Table 6, the R² value of this structural model reaches 0.357. This result shows that the extent of endogenous variation explained by the exogenous variables in this model is at a moderate level because the R² value is neither greater than 0.67 nor less than 0.33 ($0.33 > 0.357 > 0.67$). Thus, it can be said that approximately 35.7% of the financial management variable can be influenced by the variables of motivation, competence, and accountability behavior, while the remaining 64.3% is influenced by other variables that were not tested in this study. Next, the Adjusted R-square value of this structural model reaches 0.317. This result indicates that the extent of endogenous variation explained by the exogenous variables in this model is weak, as its value is not greater than 0.33 and is greater than 0.19 ($0.33 > 0.317 > 0.19$). In other words, approximately 31.7% of financial management can be explained by the variables of motivation, competence, and accountability behavior, while the remaining 68.3% is explained by other variables outside this study.

Table 7. Predictive Relevance Test (Q²) or Q-square

Variable	Q ² predict
Financial Management (Y)	0.272

Based on the Table 7, the Q² value of this study is greater than 0 and indicates that the model has predictive relevance with $Q^2 = 0.272$. This result indicates that there is predictive accuracy at a moderate or medium level, as the Q² value is greater than 0.15 ($0.272 > 0.15$).

Table 8. Path Coefficient, t-statistic, and P-Values

Hypothesis	Path Coefficient	t-statistic	P-values	Result
H ₁	0.143	0.673	0.251	H1 Rejected
H ₂	0.120	0.957	0.169	H2 Rejected
H ₃	0.422	2.235	0.013	H3 Accepted

The Table 8 shows that motivation and competence do not affect financial management, whereas accountability behavior has a positive and significant impact on financial management.

Table 9. Effect Size (F-Square)

Paths	f-square
Motivation (X1) -> Financial Management (Y)	0.019
Competence (X2)-> Financial Management (Y)	0.013
Accountability Behavior (X3) -> Financial Management (Y)	0.106

The F-square value qualitatively assesses the influence between variables on each other when significant and how strong the influence is at the structural level, namely (0.02 (weak), 0.15 (moderate), 0.35 (strong)). Based on the Table 9, there is a weak but significant influence of the accountability behavior variable (X3) on financial management (Y), so it can be said that accountability behavior has a positive effect on financial management with an f-square of 0.106. Here is the PLS bootstrapping diagram showing the path coefficients and p-value:

Figure 3. Inner Model

Motivation and Financial Management

The examination of respondents' assessments indicates that the motivation variable has an average response frequency score of 3.90, categorizing the average responses as high. Nonetheless, this fails to sufficiently represent the impact of motivation on financial management. This may be attributed to some respondents who provided unfavorable feedback; specifically, 31 respondents disagreed and 11 respondents strongly disagreed with the assertion that the bonuses and income allowances received were sufficient. Twenty-three individuals contested the assertion that their income suffices to fulfill daily living requirements. Furthermore, fourteen respondents opposed the claim that their work

is consistently evaluated objectively by the leader, and nine individuals disagreed with the statement that members are invariably provided guidance by the leader or group leader during task execution. The prevalence of negative responses from participants regarding physiological, social, and esteem needs indicates that motivation remains an ineffective variable influencing the financial management of Pokdarwis managers in the Tourism Village of Central Lombok Regency.

The demographic data indicates that the majority of respondents belong to the 36-45 age group (67.3%), while Pokdarwis managers over 46 years old were selected due to their roles as community leaders, serving as intermediaries between the community and the organization. Field observations by the researcher indicate that several managers over the age of 40 saw managing Pokdarwis as a secondary endeavor, with regular financial management not constituting a component of their routine. The managers' distrust in the sustainability of the Tourism Awareness Group is apparent among Pokdarwis managers aged 36-40, who perceive that their physiological, safety, social, esteem, and self-actualization needs remain unfulfilled by the group, thereby not influencing the organization's financial management. This correlates with the hypothesis testing results, elucidating the research findings that indicate motivation does not influence the execution of financial management within the Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis).

The findings of this test do not corroborate the Stakeholder theory, which posits that a firm or organization operates not solely for personal profit but also bears a responsibility to confer advantages to all parties involved, known as stakeholders. The stakeholders engaged include the village community, consumers, suppliers, government, and investors. This philosophy emphasizes stakeholders and their engagement in fulfilling their interests. The test results indicate that motivation has yet to affect the managers of Pokdarwis, a key stakeholder, in enhancing the quality of their financial management. The inconsequential test results may stem from various factors observed in the field, including misalignment of vision between managers and members, income levels falling short of expectations, overlapping responsibilities between Pokdarwis and the Village, inadequate member participation in policy formulation, unpersuasive assurances of organizational sustainability, and deficient rules and regulations governing the Pokdarwis organization.

The outcomes of this test are also incongruent with the conclusions of Rosnidah et al. (2022); Safwan et al. (2014); Rosalina et al. (2021); and Asah et al. (2015), which assert that motivation influences financial management. Despite the fulfillment of the desires and needs of the Pokdarwis managers, they are, in practice, incapable of enhancing the efficacy of financial planning, recording, reporting, and control. Obstacles in the area include ambiguous budget sources, managers with dual duties, insufficient comprehension of the organization's vision and mission, lack of sustainability assurance, and honorariums and salaries that fail to fulfill managers' expectations.

Competence and Financial Management

The competency variable exhibits an average response frequency of 4.23, categorizing it within the extremely high range. Nevertheless, a subset of respondents contested the assertion that the manager possesses relevant expertise in their domain, with 13

individuals indicating disagreement. Furthermore, 13 respondents expressed dissent on the assertion that the supervisors were capable of addressing complaints or grievances. In other words, some Pokdarwis managers still perceive a deficiency in the requisite knowledge and motivation to enhance their abilities and expertise pertinent to their profession. The managers' failure to address concerns and grievances indicates their continued misunderstanding of the business processes inside the Tourism Awareness Group overseeing a Tourism Village.

The characteristics of the respondents concerning their most recent education and the involvement of managers in accounting training/courses can offer insights into the hypothesis testing results, which assert that competence does not influence financial management. The proportion of Pokdarwis managers who have achieved the highest degree of education, specifically SLTA/SMA or its equivalent, is 78.9%, representing 41 respondents. Furthermore, 2 responders from the Pokdarwis managers possessed only a junior high school education, constituting 3.9%. The involvement of managers in accounting training/courses is 80.8% (42 respondents). The results indicate that certain Pokdarwis managers perceive the support from the government and organizations as inadequate, despite their desire to enhance their knowledge and skills in financial management. Consequently, Pokdarwis managers do not regard competence as significant in financial management. The managers employ distinct financial management strategies that align with their unique competencies.

The results of this research do not corroborate the Stakeholder theory, which primarily seeks to aid corporate or organizational management in augmenting value creation through conducted operations and mitigating potential losses for stakeholders. One of the initiatives undertaken is performance enhancement via effective financial management. Nevertheless, the test findings indicate that the competencies held by the managers do not affect the financial management process of a Pokdarwis. The negligible test results may stem from various factors identified by researchers during field observations, including minor issues and complaints within the business process, inadequate knowledge pertaining to business development, insufficient education and training in finance, and a limited comprehension among managers regarding the competencies essential for business sustainability.

The findings of this study align with the research by Syachbrani (2014) and Sofyani (2014), which indicates that competence does not influence performance. In contrast, the outcomes of this study diverge with the conclusions of Rosnidah et al. (2022) and Safwan et al. (2014), which assert that competence influences financial management. The conclusions of Harjanti & Utami (2022); Ningsih et al. (2023); Poernamawatie et al. (2023), which assert that ability and knowledge affect financial management, contradict the results of this study, wherein knowledge and ability serve as indicators of the competence variable. Consequently, research suggests that proficiency, expertise, and disposition do not influence the quality of financial management within the Tourism Awareness Group.

Accountability Behavior and Financial Management

The accountability behavior variable has an average response frequency value of 4.00, indicating that it falls within the high group. The average respondents rated the statement that accountability entails honesty very highly, with a score of 4.21. Moreover, the average respondents rated the statement regarding accountability and adherence to procedures at 4.31, while they scored 4.27 on the statement concerning the provision of sufficient information related to accountability. In summary, accountability significantly impacts the financial management of Pokdarwis managers. The managers are certain that adhering to the principles of accountability in financial management would enhance their organization, and they endeavor to maintain accountability in their financial practices. The gender features of respondents indicate that the majority of managers in the tourism awareness group (Pokdarwis) inside the tourist village are male, comprising 88.5%, while the involvement of women in management remains modest. The characteristics of respondents about their job experience indicate that the managers of Pokdarwis possess significant tenure in operating a tourist hamlet. Approximately 48.1% of the managers have overseen activities for 3-4 years, while 40.4% have managed the organization for over 4 years, with some managers being pioneers who founded and built the tourist town. This may represent a management approach aimed at organizational development, recognizing that men and women possess distinct perspectives and mindsets in organizational management, particularly in decision-making processes. Effective financial management necessitates prompt and precise financial decision-making, relevant experience, duration of service, and intuition. The administrators of Pokdarwis, who have long overseen a tourist village, undoubtedly recognize that accountability in planning, documenting, reporting, and financial control is a prudent strategy for sustaining both the company and the established tourist town.

The research findings align with the notion of planned behavior, which posits that behavior may be contemplated and organized, emphasizing the individual's purpose to engage in a specific action, namely accountability. Effective and efficient financial management can be achieved through accountability and adherence to its principles. Furthermore, the managers' perception of perpetual accountability will instill discipline in financial management. By comprehending the challenges, advantages, and consequences associated with the principle of accountability, managers will enhance their responsibility in financial oversight.

The findings of this study align with the research by Pratiwi et al. (2018) and Limba et al. (2020), indicating that accountability behavior influences financial management, specifically that attitudes, subjective norms, and behavioral control can impact the intention to attain transparent and accountable financial management. Consequently, it can be asserted that if the managers consistently act with accountability or adhere to the principles of accountability in planning, recording, reporting, and controlling, the financial management of Pokdarwis will become more effective and efficient.

Conclusion

From the research and discussions, it shows that only accountability behavior has a positive and significant impact on financial management. Theoretically, this research can

help clarify how the motivation, competence, and behavior of various stakeholders can influence the financial management process. Furthermore, the theory of planned behavior assumes that individual behavior is not only controlled by the individual themselves (full individual control), but also requires the availability of resources and opportunities, as well as certain skills. In this study, it helps clarify the relationship between the behavior of an organization's managers in carrying out the processes of planning, recording, reporting, and controlling in an accountable manner.

This research can assist the Central Lombok Regency Government and pertinent Ministries in assessing budgetary policies and devising enhancement strategies for the forthcoming budget cycle. Consequently, the efficacy and efficiency of budget utilization in the Tourism Villages of Central Lombok Regency can be enhanced, yielding immediate advantages for the community and expediting the development of villages and regions in a more focused and accurate manner.

The results of this research are expected to provide an overview of the importance of regulations that explain in detail related to tourist villages, tourism awareness groups, and their financial management in order to enhance the effectiveness of budget utilization and accelerate regional development through tourism, as well as to provide direct benefits to the community sustainably.

Recommendations

This research has limits that require refinement through analogous investigations about variables, data gathering methods, scope, and other factors. Consequently, elucidations on various constraints and recommendations for future research are essential to enhance understanding, particularly in the domain of behavioral accounting related to financial management. For future researchers, it is recommended to enrich the research instruments used (besides questionnaires) and to enhance the questions in the research questionnaires so that more accurate explanations related to the phenomenon on the topic of financial management can be obtained. The selection of variables used as predictors of financial management needs to be more rigorously examined through theoretical studies and references to previous research results so that the factors studied can provide more beneficial contributions to the issues of financial management, especially for the Tourism Awareness Group. Subsequent research is expected to explore other variables, such as education level, government support, and community participation, to see their impact on financial management.

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